

Insect Sex Pheromones. Stereospecific Syntheses of few Lepidoptera Pheromones containing (*E*)-Alkene Moiety

O. P. VIG*, G. L. KAD, ARUN SABHARWAL, VIJAY DOGRA and SANJIV SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

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Syntheses of few Lepidoptera sex pheromones containing (*E*)-alkene moiety have been reported utilising the modified Knoevenagel condensation and Li_2CuCl_4 catalysed coupling of Grignard reagents with alkenyl bromides.

SEX pheromones produced by moth and butterfly species (Lepidoptera) are straight chain functionalised (*E*)-alkenes of the general structure (*E*)-X-alken-1-ols, (*E*)-X-alken-1-yl acetates or (*E*)-X-alken-1-als. Examples of few such pheromones are given in Table 1. Due to their commercial importance, a number of synthetic attempts have been reported¹⁻¹⁰. All these procedures involve multisteps leading to low yields. We report here a simple and general method for the preparation of 1-6 in good yields.

Modified Knoevenagel condensation of 1-butanal with three molar excess of malonic acid and 0.001 mol of piperidinium acetate resulted in the formation of 3(*E*)-hexenoic acid¹¹ which on treatment with ethyl chloroformate/ Et_3N ¹² in anhydrous dichloromethane afforded the anhydride (7) (Scheme 1). Reduction of 7 with NaBH_4 in ethanol followed by treatment with PBr_3/Py in ether gave the bromide (9). Li_2CuCl_4 catalysed coupling¹³ of

9 with different Grignard reagents (10-12) resulted in the formation of 13-15 which upon acetylation with AcCl/AcOH and pyridine gave the desired compounds 2, 3 and 5. However, depuration of 13 and 15 gave the corresponding alcohols (1 and 4). Oxidation of the carbinol (4) with PCC in dry dichloromethane afforded the aldehyde (6). Spectral and analytical data of the synthesised pheromones were in agreement with the values reported in the literature¹⁻¹⁰.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (film) of compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CCl_4) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel (ASC, Bombay) impregnated with CaSO_4 was used for tlc. Unless otherwise stated, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

3(*E*)-Hexenoic-ethanoic anhydride (7): To an ice-cold solution of 3(*E*)-hexenoic acid (11.4 g, 100 mmol) and triethylamine (15.1 g, 149 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml), ethylchloroformate (16.2 g, 150 mmol) was added dropwise with constant stirring at 0° for 4 h (tlc monitoring). The reaction mixture was then washed with water (2 × 100 ml), extracted with dichloromethane and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography of the crude material furnished 7 (13.02 g, 70%) (Found: C, 57.9; H, 7.49. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 58.06; H, 7.52%); ν_{max} 2 900, 1 740, 1 650 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.8-1.2 (6H, m), 2.0-2.2 (2H, m), 2.8 (2H, d), 4.1 (2H, m) and 5.5-5.7 (2H, m J 7 Hz).

3(*E*)-Hexen-1-ol (8): To a well-stirred slurry of NaBH_4 (6.4 g, 200 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added the anhydride (7; 18.6 g, 100 mmol) during 1 h. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h and then acidified with dilute acetic acid till effervescence ceased. Ethanol was evaporated, the residue extracted with ether (4 × 50 ml), washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 solution, brine and dried.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—EXAMPLES OF PHEROMONES

Compd.	Species
	<i>Oeratitis capitata</i> ^a
	<i>Daucus cucurbitae</i> ^b
	<i>Diparopsis castanea</i> ^c
	<i>Archips agropyilus</i> , <i>Platynota stultana</i> , <i>Platynota idalnasalus</i> ^d
	<i>A. agropyilus</i> , <i>P. stultana</i> , <i>P. idalnasalus</i> ^e
	<i>Christoneura occidentalis</i> ^f

^aRefs. 1, 7, 8. ^bRefs. 2, 7. ^cRefs. 3, 10. ^dRefs. 4, 5, 7, 9. ^eRefs. 4, 5, 7. ^fRefs. 6, 7.

Removal of solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether as eluent gave **8** (6 g, 60%) (Found: C, 71.71; H, 11.76. $C_{18}H_{34}O$ requires: C, 72; H, 12%; ν_{max} 3 300–3 500(b), 2 900, 1 650, 1 475 and 960 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.1–1.3 (2H, m), 1.9–2.1 (4H, m), 2.5 (1H, s) and 5.4–5.6 (2H, m J 6 Hz).

1-Bromo-3(E)-hexane (9): Freshly distilled PBr_3 (2.37 ml, 24 mmol) in dry ether (15 ml) was added to the alcohol (**8**; 5 g, 50 mmol) in dry ether (100 ml) containing a small amount of pyridine and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting solution was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled, poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether (4 × 50 ml). The ethereal extract was washed with 10% aqueous $NaHCO_3$, brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent furnished **9** (4.8 g, 60%). The absence of ir band at 3 500–3 300(b) cm^{-1} confirmed the formation of bromide (**9**).

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-6(E)-nonene (13), **1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-9(E)-dodecene (14)** and **1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-11(E)-tetradecene (15)**: To a solution of different Grignard reagents (prepared from 2.72 g, 12 mmol 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy propyl bromide/2.65 g, 10 mmol 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-hexyl bromide or 2.93 g, 10 mmol 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-octyl bromide and activated Mg turnings (0.294 g, 12 mmol; 0.24 g, 10 mmol; or 0.24 g, 10 mmol in 20 ml anhydrous THF under nitrogen atmosphere), was added 1-bromo-3-(E)-hexane (**9**; 2.0 g, 12 mmol; 1.63 g, 10 mmol; or 1.63 g, 10 mmol) in anhydrous THF (10 ml) dropwise at -10° and stirred for 30 min. A catalytic amount of Li_2CuCl_4 (1.5 ml) was then added to it and stirred for 5 h at -10° , then quenched with saturated NH_4Cl (25 ml), extracted with ether (4 × 50 ml), washed with brine and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by chromatography over silica gel employing

petroleum ether–ether (9:1) as eluent gave **13** (1.34 g, 49%)/**14** (1.28 g, 48%)/**15** (1.36 g, 46%), respectively: **13** (Found: C, 74.22; H, 11.61. $C_{14}H_{26}O_2$ requires: C, 74.33; H, 11.50%; ν_{max} 2 900, 1 630, 1 475, 1 350 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.3–1.6 (12H, bs), 2.0–2.3 (4H, m), 3.3–3.6 (4H, m), 4.5 (1H, s) and 5.3–5.5 (2H, m); **14** (Found: C, 75.99; H, 12.09. $C_{17}H_{32}O_2$ requires: C, 76.11; H, 11.94%; ν_{max} 2 900, 1 650, 1 470, 1 350, 1 000 and 960 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.3–1.5 (18H, bs), 2.0–2.4 (4H, m), 3.9–4.2 (4H, m), 4.5 (1H, s) and 5.5–5.7 (2H, m); **15** (Found: C, 76.89; H, 12.01. $C_{19}H_{36}O_2$ requires: C, 77.02; H, 12.16%; ν_{max} 2 950, 1 670, 1 470, 1 350 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.3–1.5 (22H, bs), 1.9–2.2 (4H, m), 3.7–3.8 (4H, m), 4.5 (1H, s) and 5.3–5.5 (2H, m).

6(E)-Nonen-1-ol (1) and 11(E)-tetradecen-1-ol (4): A solution of **13** (1 g, 4 mmol)/**15** (1 g, 3 mmol) and PTS (0.350 g) in methanol (50 ml) was stirred for 6 h at 55° , then cooled and neutralised with solid $NaHCO_3$. Methanol was removed under reduced pressure to afford a residue which was diluted with water, extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml) and dried. The solvent was then evaporated and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether–ether (9:1) as eluent to give **1** and **4** respectively: **1** (0.35 g, 52%), b.p. $80-4^\circ/3-4$ mm (Found: C, 75.88; H, 12.53. $C_9H_{18}O$ requires: C, 76.05; H, 12.67%; ν_{max} 3 500–3 300(b), 2 900, 1 650, 1 475 and 960 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.8–0.9 (3H, t), 1.2–1.6 (6H, m), 2.1–2.4 (4H, m), 3.3–3.6 (3H, m), 5.3–5.5 (2H, m); **4** (0.35 g, 52%), b.p. $100-01^\circ/3-4$ mm (Found: C, 79.12; H, 13.02. $C_{14}H_{28}O$ requires: C, 79.29; H, 13.20%; ν_{max} 3 400–3 300b, 2 950, 1 650, 1 475 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.3–1.6 (16H, m), 1.8–2.2 (4H, m), 3.4–3.6 (3H, m) and 5.3–5.5 (2H, m).

6(*E*)-Nonen-1-yl acetate (2), 9(*E*)-dodecen-1-yl acetate (3) and 11(*E*)-tetradecen-1-yl acetate (5) : A mixture of acetyl chloride (0.8 ml, 10 mmol), acetic acid (2 ml, 36 mmol) and pyridine (0.8 ml, 9 mmol) was added to 4 (1 g, 4 mmol) at 0° dropwise during 1 h and stirred further for 12 h. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water, extracted with ether, washed with 5% NaHCO₃ and dried. Solvent was removed and the resulting solution was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) to give 2 (0.73 g, 91%), b.p. 83-4°/2-3 mm (Found : C, 71.61; H, 10.98. C₁₁H₂₀O₂ requires : C, 71.73; H, 10.86%); ν_{\max} 2900, 1740, 1650 and 970 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.7 (3H, t), 1.2-1.5 (6H, bs), 2.1 (3H, s), 2.3-2.5 (4H, m), 4.0 (2H, t) and 5.2-5.6 (2H, m).

Similarly, compounds 3 and 5 were prepared from 14 (1 g, 3 mmol) and 15 (1 g, 3 mmol) respectively : 3 (0.75 g, 89%), b.p. 115-16°/3-4 mm (Found : C, 74.15; H, 11.68. C₁₄H₂₆O₂ requires : C, 74.33; H, 11.50%); ν_{\max} 2950, 1739, 1650 and 960 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.9 (3H, t), 1.3-1.6 (12H, bs), 2.1 (3H, s), 2.2-2.6 (4H, m), 4.2 (2H, t) and 5.3-5.5 (2H, m); 5 (0.79 g, 92%) b.p. 125-26°/3-4 mm (Found : C, 75.38; H, 11.70. C₁₆H₃₀O₂ requires : C, 75.59; H, 11.81%); ν_{\max} 2850, 1750, 1650 and 970 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.9 (3H, s), 1.4-1.6 (16H, m), 1.6-2.1 (7H, m), 4.0 (2H, t) and 5.3-5.5 (2H, m).

11(*E*)-Tetradecen-1-ol (6) : A solution of 11(*E*)-tetradecenol (1 g, 4 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (5 ml) was added in one portion to a cold and stirred solution of PCC (1.54 g, 7 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (100 ml) and further stirred for about 2 h, diluted with dry ether and then

supernatant layer decanted from the black gum. The combined organic solution was passed through neutral alumina. Evaporation of solvent gave 6 (0.41 g, 60%) (Found : C, 78.89; H, 12.51; C₁₄H₂₆O requires : C, 80; H, 12.38%); ν_{\max} 2950, 1750, 1670 and 960 cm⁻¹; δ (CCl₄) 0.8 (3H, t), 1.3 (14H, bs), 2.3 (4H, m), 3.2 (2H, t), 5.4 (2H, m) and 9.7 (1H, s).

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References

1. M. JACOBSON, K. OHINATA, D. L. CHAMBERS, W. A. JONES and M. S. FUJIMOTA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1979, 16, 248.
2. M. JACOBSON, I. KEISER, D. L. CHAMBERS, D. H. MIYASHITA and C. HARDING, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 236.
3. B. F. NESBITT, P. S. BEVOR, R. A. COLE, R. LESTER and R. G. POPPI, *J. Insect. Physiol.*, 1975, 21, 1091.
4. W. L. ROELOFS, A. HILL, R. CARDE, J. TETTE, H. MADSEN and J. VEKENTI, *Environ. Entomol.*, 1975, 21, 1091.
5. A. HILL and W. L. ROELOFS, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 1975, 1, 91.
6. J. WEATHERSTEN, W. L. ROELOFS, A. COMEAU and C. SANDERS, *J. Can. Entomol.*, 1971, 103, 1741.
7. C. B. HERBERT, D. L. HSIUPER and U. K. SURENDRA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, 51, 5282.
8. O. P. VIG, M. L. SHARMA, M. GAKHAR and N. MALIK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 366.
9. O. P. VIG, M. L. SHARMA, N. K. VERMA and N. MALIK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 581, 692.
10. O. P. VIG, M. L. SHARMA, N. K. VERMA and N. MALIK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 692.
11. B. NIKITAS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, 28, 93.
12. *Organic Synth.*, 1963, 4, 285.
13. M. TAMURA and J. KOCHI, *Syntheses*, 1971, 303.